

Corpus Based Methods for Learning Models of Metaphor in Modern Greek

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Abstract. In this paper we propose a method for detecting metaphorical usage of content terms based on the hypothesis that metaphors can be detected by being characteristic of a different domain than the one they appear in. We formulate the problem as one of extracting knowledge from text classification models, where the latter have been created using standard text classification techniques without any knowledge of metaphor. We then extract from such models a measure of how characteristic of a domain a term is, providing us with a reliable method of identifying terms that are surprising for the context within which they are used. To empirically evaluate our method, we have compiled a corpus of Greek newspaper articles where the training set is only annotated with the broad thematic categories assigned by the newspapers. We have also manually annotated a test corpus with metaphorical word usage. In our experiment, we report results using tf-idf to identify the literal (characteristic) domain of terms and we also analyse the interaction between tf-idf and other typical word features, such as Part of Speech tags.

Keywords: metaphor detection · information extraction · distributional semantics · term extraction · machine learning

1 Introduction

Metaphor is a figure of non-literal usage of words that can greatly impact the accuracy of automatically analysing and interpreting language. The computational treatment of metaphor aims at *detecting* metaphor and, more ambitiously, at *interpreting* it into literal semantics.

The first efforts to detect metaphor were based on subcategorization frames and similar semantic resources to detect violations of selectional restrictions in a certain context [1, 2]. More recent systems are striving to be less demanding in the required linguistic resources and rely on more statistical approaches to semantics. The TroFi system [3], for example, assumes a user-provided set of seed sentences and detects metaphors by computing the similarity between a sentence and all of the seed sentences. Other systems rely on semantic hierarchies: Krishnakumaran and Zhu [4] for instance predict metaphorical phrases at

the sentence level using the hyponymy relation in WordNet. Also, Shutova [5] interprets metaphorical phrases as a paraphrasing task. So, for each metaphorical expression there is a literal paraphrase which is obtained by applying a probabilistic model in order to rank all the possible paraphrases of the certain metaphorical phrase at the certain context.

In the work described here we are interested in detecting *novel* metaphorical usage of content terms, excluding idiomatic metaphorical expressions. This task is motivated by *text categorization* applications, where metaphorical terminology can lead to misclassifications. Furthermore, we are interested in developing methods that can be applied to languages without rich semantic resources, such as subcategorization frame dictionaries or semantic network dictionaries. Although the ability to correctly interpret metaphors would be useful, in such a setting even detecting metaphors is a challenging task and can still be applied to exclude or reduce the weight of metaphorical terms in text categorization models.

Closer to our setting and methodology is the work by Schulder and Hovy [6] on detecting metaphors using a purely statistical approach to word semantics and the hypothesis that novel metaphoric language is *unusual* in a given context. In order to calculate whether a term is typical of its context, they use statistical metrics to identify words *commonly used in* and *characteristic of* a domain as opposed to words commonly used across all domains. They extract domain-specific document collections using term searching. The query terms are a set of seed terms that are considered typical for a domain. The evaluation of their results is based on manually chosen seed terms or the terms with the highest relevance for document search, generating a single governance domain.

In this paper we push further in the direction of minimizing the resources required in order to train the system, to present a method that only relies on having text placed in very broad thematic categories. Our use cases primarily stem in newspaper content categorization: newspaper content is organized in very broad thematic sections that can be used to detect out-of-topic, typically metaphorically used, terms. Metaphorically used terms can then be excluded or treated exceptionally in subsequent classification of the content in finer categories.

In the remainder of this paper, we first present our method (Section 2) and its implementation (Section 3). We then present the empirical evaluation of our method (Section 4) and our conclusions (Section 5).

2 Method

In the work described here, we pursue the same core hypothesis as Schulder and Hovy [6], namely, that metaphors can be detected by being characteristic of a different domain than the one they appear in. Unlike Schulder and Hovy, we do not rely on any manually chosen seed terms, neither do we formulate the problem as a classification problem where metaphor annotation is the output of a classifier.

Instead, we formulate the problem as one of *extracting knowledge* from text classification models, where the latter have been created using standard text classification techniques without any knowledge of metaphor. We then extract from such models a measure of how characteristic of a domain a term is, providing us with a reliable method of identifying terms that are *uncharacteristic* of the context within which they are used.

By doing this, we build upon the rich text classification literature and the robustness of its statistical methods in identifying domain-characteristic terms versus terms that are generally frequent across all domains. Furthermore, we provide a methodology that does not rely on any seeds or other semantic resources at the level of individual terms, but only on building a classifier that predicts very broad thematic annotations for complete articles, such as the ‘politics’, ‘sports’, and similar categories readily available in any newspaper corpus. This methodology does not require sentence structure information or semantic resources and can be applied to less-resourced languages, is robust to noisy data, and is efficient enough to be applied on large-scale corpora.

In the experiments presented here, we instantiate this generic methodology using the *Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency (tf-idf)* of the terms appearing in a document as features for *language models* that predict the domain based on the document terms. tf-idf balances between the frequency of a term in a particular context (tf) and its frequency across all contexts (idf) and is very well suited for identifying ‘surprising’ words in a given context.

In our experiments we used a *Maximum Likelihood Classifier* that uses term weighting as its only metric to assume that the ‘native’ or literal-usage domain of a term is the one where it weights the most.

3 Implementation

3.1 Corpus Collection and Preprocessing

In order to investigate our research proposal we started with compiling a corpus of articles from three Greek newspapers that offer content on-line: ‘Lefkaditika Nea’, ‘Thraki’, and ‘Avgi’. In order to have an initial classification, we mapped the sections of these three newspapers to domains from the top level of the relevant taxonomy of the *International Press Telecommunications Council (IPTC)*.³ Table 1 lists the seven domains and the number of articles in each.

The articles of the corpus were downloaded from the web as HTML files and cleaned into plain text using the Boilerpipe library [7]. After tokenization and stopword removal, we dropped tokens that consist of single alphanumeric characters and several symbols. Then, we converted each word to upper case without the Greek diacritics to avoid confusion. After the initial processing, we had to detect the stems of our data.

Although there is a variety of stemmers, the unique morphological system of each language doesn’t allow the creation of a global rule-based algorithm which

³ Please cf. www.iptc.org for more details.

IPTC code	Domain	Number	Percentage
01000000	Art, Culture and Entertainment	3178	20.2%
04000000	Economy,Business and Finance	3132	20.0%
06000000	Environment	693	4.4%
07000000	Health	771	4.9%
11000000	Politics	6618	42.2%
13000000	Science and Technology	210	1.3%
15000000	Sport	1100	7.0%
	All corpus	15702	

Table 1. Distribution of articles in topics.

would be able to find out the stem of each word. Especially, in some languages with a rich morphological system, like Greek, it is even more difficult to find the word stem by reducing the suffix from inflected or derived words. It is useful to mention that a wide variety of suffixes exist in the Greek morphological system, some of them may appear in different parts of speech. For this reason, it is necessary to point out the part of speech of the certain word before trying to find out the root of the concrete word. Our stemmer is available on-line.⁴

Text Feature Extraction of Term Weighting in Corpus: Metric TF-IDF

Term weighting is an important aspect of IR systems. Terms are words, phrases or any other indexing units used to identify the contents of a text. Since different terms have different level of importance in a text, an important indicator, which is called (*term weight*), is associated with each term. Three main components that affect the importance of a term in a text are the *term frequency factor (tf)*, the *inverse document frequency factor (idf)* and the *normalization factor*. More specifically:

- *term frequency factor (tf)*: Long documents usually use the same terms repeatedly. As a result, the term frequency factors may be large for long documents, increasing the average contribution of its terms towards the query - document similarity.
- *inverse document frequency factor (idf)*: Long documents also have numerous different terms. This increases the number of matches between a query and a long document, increasing the query - document similarity and the chances of retrieval of long documents in preference over short documents. Moreover, the high rate of appearance of a word doesn't imply that this word is directly related to the topic of the specific document. The word with the highest occurrence rate may be an auxiliary verb, like the Greek verb *eimai* ('to be'). For this reason, the *inverse document frequency (idf)* is used,

⁴ Please see <https://bitbucket.org/dataengineering/stemming>

which is based on counting the number of documents in the collection being searched which contain the term in question.

- *Normalization factor*: is a way of penalizing the term weights for a document in accordance with its length. Normalization factor retain the number of featured terms, normalizing the weights and ensuring that all their values are between 0 and 1. The use of a logarithmic function in the TF-IDF equation constitutes the normalization factor.

As a consequence, in order to calculate the weight of a term of the domain, we use the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tf-idf}(t, d) &= \text{tf}(t, d) \text{idf}(t, d) \\ &= \frac{\text{freq}(t, d)}{|T_d|} \log \frac{|D|}{|D_t|} \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{freq}(t, d)$ is the frequency of term t in domain d , T_d is the set of terms appearing in domain d , D is the set of domains, and D_t is the set of domains where t appears. At this point we should mention that we adapted this method by treating all texts of a domain as a single ‘document’.

Terms with a great impact receive high scores, while low scores are assigned to words that are either not frequent in the document or otherwise are too frequent among documents.

3.2 Classification

The *Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC)* is one of the most popular methods of classification in text/word classification, in which a text/word with the maximum likelihood is classified into the corresponding class. We use MLC in order to determine probabilistically the domain of a word. Specifically, we have already estimated the TF-IDF value of words for each domain. Each word is classified in the domain where it appears with the highest TF-IDF value. More formally, given a term t and the set d_t of all the domains where t appears:

$$\text{MLC}(t, d_t) = \text{argmax}_{d \in d_t} \text{tf-idf}(t, d)$$

If a term has zero TF-IDF values for all domains, then this term remained unclassified and was not used in the procedure of metaphor detection. Also, if a term had almost the same probability to belong in more than one literal domains, that term was classified to all these possible domains.

4 Empirical Evaluation

In order to evaluate our method, we have manually annotated 10 articles from the corpus described above. The manual annotation was carried out by two initial annotators, with a third expert annotator resolving inconsistencies to create the

Fig. 1. Processing stages.

golden corpus. Table 2 gives some statistics about this golden test corpus. Besides the metaphor span, the annotators have also marked each metaphor as being an instance of one of the following types:

Indirect, lexical metaphors that operate at the level of a single word where a term identifies metaphorically another term which is literal. Characteristic examples include:

- (1) *magika nisia*
magic islands
- (2) *Omirikoi kavgades*
Homeric quarrels
fierce quarrels

Multi-word metaphorical expressions where a new meaning is obtained by combining all the constituents of the certain phrase. Characteristic examples include:

- (3) *Evale to heri tou*
put-3ps the hand his-CLITIC
He helped
- (4) *evale freno*
put-3ps brake
He slowed down

Direct or is-a metaphors where the copula connects the subject with a non-literal complement, such as ‘time is money’. And, finally, *idiomatic metaphorical expressions*, such as ‘kick the bucket’.

Metaphor spans can possibly overlap as in the example below:

- (5) *[[Rokanizontas dramatika] ton rolo] tou tupografou*
Shaving (carpentry) dramatically the role the typographer-GEN
Dramatically gnawing at the typographer’s role

where neither ‘dramatically gnawing’ nor ‘gnawing at the role’ are interpreted literally.

Our method yields single-word binary decisions about metaphorical usage. Following standard practice, we define *precision*, *recall* as follows:

IPTC	All words	Content words	Metaphors
01000000	567	312	11
04000000	756	411	32
04000000	619	323	29
04000000	1158	650	34
07000000	321	169	13
11000000	760	414	51
11000000	961	518	52
11000000	715	404	15
11000000	985	558	50
11000000	987	546	53
All articles	7829	4305	340

Table 2. Annotated articles.

- Precision is the percentage of positive decisions that were inside at least one span annotated as metaphor.
- Recall is the percentage of spans annotated as metaphors that include at least one positive decision.

F_1 -score is defined in the usual manner over this precision and recall.

Moreover, we tested how metaphor detection interacts with words’ features, such as specific PoS (Noun, Verb, Adjective). Specifically, except for total number of words, we evaluated our model for the three PoS separately (Table 3). The performance of the recall for specific PoS seems slightly disappointing at first, if it is compared with the recall of All PoS. This fact is explained as each metaphor phrase is very likely to contain one of each PoS.

Also, we evaluated our system only with the words which appear to have the strongest impact (Table 4, Figure 2). For 24,463 classified words, we used only the 8,154 words with the highest TF-IDF value in order to detect the non literal phrases. The results are slightly different from the previous experiment. Precision and Recall follow opposite behavior. Fewer classified words result to fewer detected metaphors (demote recall) and fewer false positives (improve precision), too. Nevertheless, this experiment achieves the best performance for the precision.

The vocabulary of the model comprises 28,305 unique words. The 24,463 of these words are classified using the MLC classifier. The remaining 3,842 words have zero tf-idf and are left unclassified. Trying to improve our system we estimate a alternative method to exploit these unclassified words. We set a rule which classify each word depending on the term frequency (calculated as in tf-idf above) and *document frequency* (df). Document frequency of term t in document collection C is defined as the average number of occurrences of t in

	All PoS	Noun	Adjective	Verb
Precision	0.410	0.424	0.509	0.340
Recall	0.494	0.242	0.355	0.209
$F_{\beta=1}$	0.448	0.308	0.419	0.258

Table 3. Evaluation results.

	All PoS	Noun	Adjective	Verb
Precision	0.443	0.421	0.597	0.555
Recall	0.285	0.150	0.209	0.066
$F_{\beta=1}$	0.347	0.221	0.300	0.119

Table 4. Evaluation results for the 1/3 of all the terms with the highest TF-IDF value.

each document of C :

$$\text{df}(t, C) = \frac{\text{freq}(t, C)}{|C|}$$

We then categorize terms with a low df (threshold determined empirically) using tf instead of tf-idf. Of the 3,842 unclassified words because if zero if-idf, we used this to classify 2,037 additional words (Table 5). Although precision is slightly worse, increased recall improves the overall F_1 -score.

In order to investigate the influence of the number of classified words in model, we trained a model with larger vocabulary, and 40,723 classifies words. The improvement in Precision, Recall and F1 was tiny. As a result, we accept the previous model which retain approximately the same performance with lower complexity and cost.

A word with low TF-IDF might also indicate a word that is common among all domains. To filter out such candidates, we use document frequency as additional feature. We exclude word with high document frequency, but the results were not so promising.

There are a lot of cases that a word belongs to more than one literal domain. Thus, we try to build a more robust model, using alternative approach of classification. We classify each term in the two most probably domains, but our results did not improved.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we presented a statistical methodology for detecting metaphorical usage of content words. The main advantage of our methodology is that it only relies on a corpus of documents assigned to broad thematic categories and does not require any other semantic resources. This gives our method a very wide scope of application across less-resourced languages.

	All PoS	Noun	Adjective	Verb
Precision	0.397	0.445	0.483	0.285
Recall	0.629	0.346	0.432	0.322
$F_{\beta=1}$	0.487	0.389	0.456	0.303

Table 5. Evaluation results for 26,500 classified words.

Fig. 2. Evaluation results for the terms with the highest TF-IDF value.

For our experiments we have used a newspaper corpus assuming the topics under which articles were posted as such thematic categories. We experimented with the F_1 -score obtained by our method and found significant variation between the various Parts of Speech. Thus, we had the opportunity to study the structure of the Greek articles, to find out words which can be used as non literal indicators and to detect common words which are used to appear at more than one article’s domains and so they don’t have any value for contribution to differentiation between literal and non literal speech.

For future work we plan to revisit our experiments with more test data of different domains. The vast majority of articles currently belong to ‘Art, Culture and Entertainment’, ‘Economy, Business and Finance’ and ‘Politics’. The latter two are the hardest domains in that they encompass several themes and might use words from different domains literally. Domains such as ‘Sport’ and ‘Health’ on the other hand are more amenable to our approach, but have considerably fewer articles (Table 1). We are continuing the article collection and pre-processing as more articles become available, in the hope that a larger dataset will include enough articles from all domains to allow a more thorough statistical investigation of the differences between domains.

Furthermore, a larger dataset will allow us to increase the order of our models to bigrams or trigrams without encountering severe data sparsity problems.

This will allow us to experiment with detecting more complex metaphorical construction that cannot be captured by uni-term models.

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